

Synthesis of some new α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)-2-azetidinones by conventional and microwave methods and their spermicidal, antimicrobial activities

Sharda Sharma*, Harsha Madan and Arvind Sharma

Department of Chemistry, Govt. P.G. College, Kota-324 006, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : sharda_ak@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : α -Oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)-2-azetidinones were prepared by reaction of appropriate α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)ethanhydrazones and acetyl chloride/chloroacetyl chloride in dimethyl formamide (DMF). The reactions have been carried out by conventional and microwave methods. All the prepared compounds were characterized by their elemental analysis and spectral (IR, ^1H NMR, mass) data. The compounds have been evaluated for their spermicidal activity in semen of Holstein Friesian cattle, antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Keywords : Azetidinones, Staudinger reaction, microwave irradiation, β -lactam.

Introduction

A comprehensive study of fluorinated *N*-aryl- α -arylethanhydrazones and related compounds had already been reported by us¹⁻⁴. The 2-azetidinone nucleus is well known for its pharmacological properties viz. anti-inflammatory, antidegenerative⁵, antimicrobial⁶⁻⁸, antibiotics^{9,10} and several other biological activities like blood platelet aggregate inhibitors¹¹.

Microwave irradiation, although occasionally known by such acronyms as 'MEC' (Microwave-Enhanced Chemistry) or *MORE synthesis* (Microwave-organic Reaction Enhancement), is becoming an increasingly popular method of heating which replaces the classical one as it proves to be a clean, cheap and convenient method^{12,13}. This method of heating has been extended to almost all areas of organic chemistry¹⁴. Under Staudinger reaction in the normal condition, the products configuration and yield appear to be affected by several factors, including solvent, temperature, base, and the sequence of dripping of reagents. Although the acyl chloride-imine reaction is a well-established method for the synthesis of β -lactam, modifications that improve the yield, shorten synthetic time and decrease the cost are important in light of the biological significance of β -lactam. The microwave procedure for the synthesis of azetidinones **3** and **4** owes its importance due to fact that the reaction is complete within

180–250 s as compared to conventional method, which requires 5–9 h heating.

Keeping in view of these findings we have now synthesized and characterized a series of substituted 2-azetidinones **3(a-d)** and **4(a-d)** (Scheme 1) by both conventional and microwave method. A comparative study in terms of reaction time and yield of compound **3** and **4** under microwave and conventional method is reported in Table 1.

The compounds have been evaluated for their spermicidal activity in semen of Holstein Friesian cattle, antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Results and discussion

α -Oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)-2-azetidinones **3(a-d)** were synthesized by reaction of appropriate α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)ethanhydrazones **2(a-d)** and acetyl chloride/chloroacetyl chloride in dimethyl formamide (DMF) by microwave and conventional methods.

The IR spectrum of **2(a-d)** exhibited absorption peak in the region 3240–3200 cm^{-1} due to NH group, a peak at 1640 cm^{-1} due to highly conjugated C=O group and at 1610 cm^{-1} due to C=N group. In ^1H NMR a broad sing-

Scheme 1

Table 1. Physical, analytical data and results of synthesis of α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)-2-azetidinones

Compd.	X	Mol. formulae	Time		M.p. (°C)	Yield		N (%)	
			m.w. method	Classical method		m.w. method	Classical method	Found	Calcd
3a	4-F	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ F	180	6	246	75	65	9.81	9.86
3b	2-Cl, 4-F	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ ClF	240	8	258	70	55	8.61	8.80
3c	4-F, 2-CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₅ N ₂ O ₂ F	200	7	249	68	53	9.34	9.39
3d	4-F, 5-CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₅ N ₂ O ₂ F	200	8	252	70	50	9.31	9.39
4a	4-F	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ ClF	240	7	259	76	68	8.62	8.80
4b	2-Cl, 4-F	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Cl ₂ F	240	8	264	72	52	7.83	7.95
4c	4-F, 2-CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ ClF	220	8	272	68	50	8.23	8.43
4d	4-F, 5-CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ ClF	230	7	276	65	45	8.23	8.43

let appears between δ 11.0–12.0 ppm due to NH proton which disappears on deuterium oxide exchange. All aromatic protons appear as a multiplet between δ 6.8–8.5 ppm. Further support for proposed structure is based on mass spectral studies. In the IR spectra of compound 3(a-d) and 4(a-d), disappearance of C=N bond at 1610–1600 cm⁻¹ and appearance of another carbonyl absorption band at 1725–1700 cm⁻¹ (unconjugated C=O) indicates the complete cyclisation of the hydrazones 2 into α -oxo-*N*-

phenyl-aryl-2-azetidinones. In addition to this appearance of a doublet for -CH₂ protons and a triplet for -CH- proton of the azetidinone ring between δ 3–4 ppm in the ¹H NMR confirms the formation of compound 3(a-d). All the aromatic proton resonance signals are spread over δ 6.9–8.0 ppm. ¹H NMR spectra of compound 4(a-d) exhibited a double doublet of the two hydrogen on the azetidinone ring in the region δ 2.9–4.0 ppm. All the compounds have also been characterized by mass spec-

tral studies by their molecular ion peak which corresponds to their molecular weights. Spectral data of compounds 3(a-d) and 4(a-d) are in harmony with proposed structures.

Spermicidal activity: Compounds 3a, 3b, 4a, 4b were evaluated for spermicidal activity, following sperm motility scheme¹⁵. Briefly the motility of sperms was observed under 40x magnification of light microscope in a cell counting chamber. While observing the motility, 25 μ L solution (compound + alcohol) was added to the 25 μ L semen and it was observed that addition of compound 3 and 4 to semen produces a reduction of sperm motility in HF cattle spermatozoa, which was dose and time dependent. At 100 ppm concentration of compound 3a, HF cattle sperm motility was reduced to 5% in 3 min. Compound 3b at 100 ppm inhibited motility to 50% in 5 min. After 4 min, sperm motility was reduced to 40% by compound 4a whereas 4b compound reduces the motility to 70% in 3.4 min at 100 ppm concentration only. The results have been summarized in Table 2 and shown by Fig. 1.

Table 2. Spermicidal activity

Compd.	Dose (ppm)	Motility (%)	Time (min)	Base
3a	100	5	3	Alcohol
3b	100	50	5	Alcohol
4a	100	40	4	Alcohol
4b	100	70	3.4	Alcohol

Fig. 1. Spermicidal activity.

Antimicrobial activity:

The compounds have been evaluated for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and antifungal activity

against *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum* at different concentration by disk diffusion method¹⁶. Gentamycin and mycostatin were used as reference compounds for evaluating antibacterial and antifungal activities, respectively. Compounds 4(a-d) showed enhanced antibacterial and antifungal activity at concentration 200, 400, 800, 1000 ppm due to presence of chlorine atom in β -lactam ring. The results obtained are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

Experimental

General: Melting points were determined in open glass capillary tube and are uncorrected. IR spectra (cm^{-1}) were recorded on FTIR Nicolet Magna 550 and Shimadzu 8400S spectrophotometer in KBr disc and noteworthy absorptions levels (cm^{-1}) were listed. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on JEOL AL 300 MHz FT NMR instrument, ν in cm^{-1} . Mass spectra were determined by JEOL SX-102 spectrometer. TLC using silica gel G as adsorbent checked the purity of the compounds, UV light or iodine accomplished visualization.

Compound 2 was prepared by reported method¹.

Synthesis of 3(a-d) by conventional method:

To the 10 ml of stirring dimethyl formamide (DMF), 2 mmol of acetyl chloride and 2 mmol of azomethine i.e. α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)ethanhydrazones were added and solution was heated to reflux for 6–8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with 50 ml of water and was extracted with 25 ml of dichloromethane or chloroform. The organic layer was dried and evaporated in vacuum. It afforded oil or a crystalline residue, which after recrystallization from ethanol afforded β -lactams i.e. α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)-2-azetidinones.

Synthesis of 4(a-d) by conventional method:

To the 10 ml of stirring dimethyl formamide (DMF), 2 mmol of chloroacetyl chloride and 2 mmol of azomethine i.e. α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)ethanhydrazones were added and solution was heated to reflux for 6–8 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with 50 ml of water and was extracted with 25 ml of dichloromethane or chloroform. The organic layer was dried and evaporated in vacuum. It afforded oil or a crystalline residue that after recrystallization from ethanol afforded β -lactams i.e. α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)-2-azetidinones.

Table 3. Antibacterial activity of α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)-2-azetidinones

Bacteria → Gentamycin → Compd. ↓	Mean value of area of inhibition in mm 1000			Mean value of area of inhibition in mm 800			Mean value of area of inhibition in mm 400			Mean value of area of inhibition in mm 200		
	ppm IZ (AI)			ppm IZ (AI)			ppm IZ (AI)			ppm IZ (AI)		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
3a	5.4 (0.54)	6.0 (0.86)	5.1 (0.42)	5.0 (0.58)	3.0 (0.46)	3 (0.30)	4.6 (0.60)	2.6 (0.43)	3.2 (0.37)	4.0 (0.55)	2.1 (0.38)	2.8 (0.36)
3b	7.4 (0.74)	7.6 (1.1)	5.5 (0.45)	6.6 (0.76)	3.7 (0.57)	5.1 (0.51)	6.2 (0.81)	3.8 (0.63)	4.5 (0.52)	5.8 (0.80)	3.1 (0.57)	4.2 (0.55)
3c	6.5 (0.65)	6.3 (0.91)	5.2 (0.43)	5.5 (0.63)	3.2 (0.50)	5 (0.5)	5.2 (0.68)	3 (0.5)	3.5 (0.41)	4.6 (0.63)	2.3 (0.42)	4.4 (0.57)
3d	6.9 (0.69)	7.2 (1.04)	5.3 (0.44)	6.0 (0.69)	3.5 (0.54)	4.8 (0.48)	5.8 (0.76)	3.4 (0.56)	3.7 (0.43)	5.2 (0.72)	2.7 (0.50)	3.4 (0.44)
4a	8.1 (0.81)	8.2 (1.18)	4.3 (0.35)	7.0 (0.81)	5.2 (0.81)	5.1 (0.51)	6.5 (0.85)	5.0 (0.83)	4.8 (0.56)	6.2 (0.86)	3.4 (0.62)	4.4 (0.57)
4b	9.5 (0.95)	9.4 (1.36)	7.5 (0.62)	8.6 (1.0)	7.2 (1.12)	7.2 (0.72)	8.2 (1.07)	5.8 (0.96)	6.5 (0.76)	7.8 (1.08)	5.3 (0.98)	6.1 (0.80)
4c	8.4 (0.84)	8.5 (1.23)	5.3 (0.44)	7.2 (0.83)	5.6 (0.87)	5.2 (0.52)	7.0 (0.92)	5.4 (0.9)	5.2 (0.61)	6.8 (0.94)	4.2 (0.77)	5.0 (0.65)
4d	9.1 (0.91)	9.0 (1.30)	5.7 (0.47)	7.8 (0.90)	6.3 (0.98)	5.5 (0.55)	7.5 (0.98)	5.6 (0.93)	5.8 (0.68)	7.2 (1.0)	5.1 (0.94)	5.0 (0.65)

IZ = Inhibition area excluding diameter of disk.

AI = Activity index = Inhibition area of sample/Inhibition area of standard.

A = *Staphylococcus aureus*, B = *Escherichia coli*, C = *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Table 4. Antifungal activity of α -oxo-*N*-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)-2-azetidinones

Fungi → Mycostatin → Compd. ↓	Mean value of area of inhibition in mm 1000			Mean value of area of inhibition in mm 800			Mean value of area of inhibition in mm 400			Mean value of area of inhibition in mm 200		
	ppm IZ (AI)			ppm IZ (AI)			ppm IZ (AI)			ppm IZ (AI)		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
3a	6.4 (0.8)	8.4 (0.70)	5.1 (0.66)	5.8 (0.82)	7.8 (0.77)	4.0 (0.55)	5.4 (0.83)	7.0 (0.76)	2.4 (0.37)	5.0 (0.83)	6.2 (0.74)	2.1 (0.38)
3b	6.3 (0.78)	9.1 (0.75)	5.7 (0.74)	6.2 (0.88)	8.5 (0.84)	5.3 (0.73)	5.8 (0.89)	7.8 (0.85)	3.7 (0.57)	5.5 (0.91)	7.0 (0.84)	3.4 (0.62)
3c	6.2 (0.77)	8.5 (0.70)	5.4 (0.70)	6.0 (0.85)	8.0 (0.79)	4.3 (0.59)	5.5 (0.84)	7.4 (0.81)	3.2 (0.50)	5.1 (0.85)	6.8 (0.81)	2.7 (0.50)
3d	6.7 (0.83)	8.8 (0.73)	5.2 (0.67)	6.0 (0.85)	8.5 (0.84)	4.7 (0.65)	5.8 (0.89)	7.5 (0.82)	3.5 (0.54)	5.2 (0.86)	7.3 (0.87)	3.1 (0.57)
4a	7.3 (0.91)	9.4 (0.78)	5.9 (0.76)	7.1 (1.01)	8.6 (0.85)	5.5 (0.76)	6.0 (0.92)	7.9 (0.86)	5.2 (0.81)	5.8 (0.96)	7.5 (0.9)	5.1 (0.94)

Note

Table-4 (contd.)

4b	8.3 (1.03)	9.6 (0.8)	6.6 (0.85)	7.8 (1.11)	9.2 (0.91)	6.9 (0.95)	7.0 (1.07)	8.6 (0.94)	6.4 (1.0)	6.8 (1.13)	8.5 (1.02)	5.9 (1.09)
4c	7.5 (0.93)	9.1 (0.75)	6.1 (0.79)	7.0 (1.0)	8.7 (0.86)	5.8 (0.80)	6.5 (1.0)	8.1 (0.89)	5.6 (0.87)	6.0 (1.0)	7.8 (0.93)	5.3 (0.98)
4d	8.1 (1.01)	9.2 (0.76)	6.3 (0.81)	7.6 (1.08)	9.0 (0.89)	6.4 (0.88)	6.5 (1.0)	8.4 (0.92)	6.1 (0.95)	6.3 (1.05)	8.1 (0.97)	5.5 (1.01)

IZ = Inhibition area excluding diameter of disk.

AI = Activity index = Inhibition area of sample/Inhibition area of standard.

A = *Aspergillus niger*, B = *Fusarium oxysporum*, C = *Candida albicans*.

Synthesis of 3(a-d) by microwave method :

In the microwave synthetical experiment, we selected low, middle and high power of microwave irradiation respectively (the commercial LG domestic microwave oven only has three choices).

Mixture of azomethine i.e. α -oxo-N-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)ethanhydrazone (2 mmol) and acetyl chloride (2 mmol) in dimethyl formamide (DMF) (10 ml) was irradiated at 300 W (25% mW power) under microwave irradiation for 2–5 min with a short interval of 5 to 30 s to avoid excess evaporation of solvent. After completion of reaction checked by TLC, the reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with 50 ml of water and was extracted with 25 ml of dichloromethane and kept under refrigeration. The resultant sticky product was filtered, washed with water (3 × 25 ml), dried and recrystallized with ethanol.

Synthesis of 4(a-d) by microwave method :

Mixture of azomethine i.e. α -oxo-N-phenyl-(4-fluoroaryl)ethanhydrazone (2 mmol) and chloroacetyl chloride (2 mmol) in dimethyl formamide (DMF) (10 ml) was irradiated at 300 W (25% mW power) under microwave irradiation for 2–5 min with a short interval of 5 to 30 s to avoid excess evaporation of solvent. After completion of reaction checked by TLC, the reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with 50 ml of water and was extracted with 25 ml of dichloromethane and kept under refrigeration. The resultant sticky product was filtered washed with water (3 × 25 ml) dried and recrystallized with ethanol.

Spectral data :

α -Oxo-N-phenyl-(4-fluorophenyl)-2-azetidinone (3a) : m.p. 246 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3240 (NH), 1725 (C=O), 1640 (conjugated C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ

(ppm)] : 3.2 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$), 3.9 (1H, t, $-\text{CH}$), 7.1–7.9 (9H, m, Ar-R) (Found : C, 67.58; H, 4.53; N, 9.81. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{F}$: C, 67.60; H, 4.57; N, 9.86%); MS (m/z) : 284 [$\text{M}]^+$.

α -Oxo-N-phenyl-(2-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-2-azetidinone (3b) : m.p. 258 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O), 1640 (conjugated C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.3 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$), 4.0 (1H, t, $-\text{CH}$), 7.1–8.0 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 60.33; H, 3.75; N, 8.61. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{ClF}$: C, 60.37; H, 3.77; N, 8.80%); MS (m/z) : 318 [$\text{M}]^+$.

α -Oxo-N-phenyl-(4-fluoro-2-methylphenyl)-2-azetidinone (3c) : m.p. 249 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3210 (NH), 1718 (C=O), 1640 (conjugated C=O) ; ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.1 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$), 3.7 (1H, t, $-\text{CH}$), 1.5 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 6.9–7.9 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 68.40; H, 5.01; N, 9.34. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{F}$: C, 68.45; H, 5.03; N, 9.39%); MS (m/z) : 298 [$\text{M}]^+$.

α -Oxo-N-phenyl-(4-fluoro-5-methylphenyl)-2-azetidinone (3d) : m.p. 252 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3200 (NH), 1710 (C=O), 1640 (conjugated C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.1 (2H, d, $-\text{CH}_2$), 3.7 (1H, t, $-\text{CH}$), 1.5 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 6.9–7.9 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 68.40; H, 5.01; N, 9.31. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{F}$: C, 68.45; H, 5.03; N, 9.39%); MS (m/z) : 298 [$\text{M}]^+$.

α -Oxo-N-phenyl-(4-fluorophenyl)-3-chloro-2-azetidinone (4a) : m.p. 259 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3230 (NH), 1722 (C=O), 1640 (conjugated C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.0–3.9 (2H, dd, $>\text{CH}-\text{CH}<$), 7.1–8.0 (9H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 60.33; H, 4.55; N, 8.62. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{ClF}$: C, 60.37; H, 3.77; N, 8.80%); MS (m/z) : 318 [$\text{M}]^+$.

α-Oxo-N-phenyl-(2-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-3-chloro-2-azetidinone (4b) : m.p. 264 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3220 (NH), 1720 (C=O), 1640 (conjugated C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 3.1–3.8 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 7.2–8.0 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 53.9; H, 3.01; N, 7.83. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{F}$: C, 54.5; H, 3.12; N, 7.95%); MS (m/z) : 352 $[\text{M}]^+$.

α-Oxo-N-phenyl-(4-fluoro-2-methylphenyl)-3-chloro-2-azetidinane (4c) : m.p. 272 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3210 (NH), 1718 (C=O), 1640 (conjugated C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 2.9–4.0 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 1.5 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 6.9–7.9 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 61.39; H, 4.15; N, 8.23. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{ClF}$: C, 61.44; H, 4.21; N, 8.43%); MS (m/z) : 332 $[\text{M}]^+$.

α-Oxo-N-phenyl-(4-fluoro-5-methylphenyl)-3-chloro-2-azetidinones (4d) : m.p. 276 °C; IR (KBr, ν cm^{-1}) : 3210 (NH), 1718 (C=O), 1640 (conjugated C=O); ^1H NMR [300 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ (ppm)] : 2.9–4.0 (2H, dd, >CH-CH<), 1.5 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 6.9–7.9 (8H, m, Ar-H) (Found : C, 61.39; H, 4.15; N, 8.23. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{ClF}$: C, 61.44; H, 4.21; N, 8.43%); MS (m/z) : 332 $[\text{M}]^+$.

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